

Characterizing smallholder organic vegetable farming practices in a Mountainous Area in the Philippines

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Abstract

The research described the attributes of smallholder organic vegetable farmers, their production practices and problems and best practices as bases for policy directions to ensure the sustainability of small-hold organic vegetable farming in the CAR. Survey, using a researcher-made questionnaire was the primary data gathering technique. Thirty one (31) farmers were personally interviewed and an ocular inspection of their organic farms to observe their production practices was undertaken. Telephone inquiries or short messaging system (SMS) were also utilized when some information were missed out during the interview and to verify vague and incomplete information. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages and means/averages were used to qualify and summarize data. Although farming is typically a man's world, more women and more professionals are increasingly been involved in smallholder farming and in organic agriculture, in general. The average age of 46 indicates that the farmers just recently shifted to organic farming or have had careers prior to farming. The farmers cultivate an average area of not more than 600 square meters deriving an average annual net income of P98,387.39. Production is described as a system where different kinds or varieties of vegetables are raised in complement with or intercropped with the others to maximize the production area. Natural calamities, pest management, production inputs, lack of capital, plant management, lack of manpower and irrigation are major production constraints. Despite these constraints, best practices had been documented that could sustain smallholder organic vegetable production in the CAR.

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Introduction

Organic agriculture (OA) is a form of farming which relies on natural processes rather than synthetic inputs to enhance crop production. These natural processes include crop rotation, green manures and composting techniques which enhance soil productivity and control pests and diseases. Organic farming is promoted because of its impact on the environment by reducing pollution, conserving water, reducing soil erosion, increasing soil fertility and using less energy. In organic farming, there is reduced dependence on chemical inputs making it more environmentally sustainable than conventional farming. These all contribute in strengthening biodiversity in the environment. A thriving biodiversity increases ecosystem productivity and allows the growth and maintenance of various species.

The Philippines, because it possesses diverse ecological zones, is an ideal ground for organic farming. Organic farming has been successfully implemented in the country and supported by the government with the enactment of the Organic Agriculture Act of 2010 (Republic Act No. 10068) as amended by Republic Act No. 11511 in 2021. Under these Acts, it is the State's policy to "promote, propagate, develop further and implement the practice of organic agriculture." This is in order to increase farm productivity and farmers' incomes, encourage the participation of indigenous organic farmers in promoting their sustainable practices, and protect the health of farmers, consumers and the public, among others. Furthermore, the State also recognizes and supports the role of farmers, indigenous peoples and other stakeholders who are at the grassroots of this program. RA No. 11511 specifically enhances the role of community-based organic agriculture systems to promote organic agriculture. The country has a long history of organic agriculture where traditional Filipino farmers have always relied on organic methods to raise rice, corn, vegetables and even fruits. However, modern agricultural practices have made most of them turn from these traditions to rely on synthetic inputs like chemicals fertilizer and pesticides (Lapniten, 2020).

With the enactment of the OA Acts of 2010 and 2021, the National Organic Agriculture Program (NOAP) was crafted which contains strategic plans to promote organic agriculture in the country. It is referred to as the blueprint of the Department of Agriculture, the implementing agency of OA. As of December 2016, NOAP data on OA show that 4.86% of the country's agricultural land was converted to organic farmland. The Regions, particularly Region 13, 3, 12, 11 and CAR have reached 100% of their 5% target of organic area. Total volume of production was 525,863 metric tons distributed across 86 domestic and 20 export markets. Farmer-beneficiaries was registered at 116,558 representing 63 certified farmers and establishments, with 88 pending applications. By the end of 2023, NOAP aims to increase the area covered for OA to 501,887.09 hectares from 349,041, increase the number of certified operators to 340, bring the number of total organic practitioners to 233,100 and increase total production volume to 756,300 metric tons, distributed across national and international channels (NOAP, 2018).

The Cordillera Administrative Region (CAR) is among the first regions in the Philippines to engage in organic agriculture and one of the biggest supplier of organic vegetables in the market. Based on 2016 data, CAR has a total of 26, 128.71 hectares of organic production area with over 2,000 organic practitioners and 51 duly recognized associations. Organic farms in the Philippines are typically small-scale and family-run, which is basically true in the CAR. Due to its topography, which is mountainous with towering peaks, plateaus and intermittent patches of valley where 71% of its land area has slopes of 30 degrees and above (PSA, 2020), the availability of arable land is limited. Thus, majority of the organic producers till only a small parcel of land often referred to as gardens. These are areas outside of buffer zones of farms utilized for conventional production of vegetables and other products. They are usually located in sloping terrains or in patches of flat lands terraced, ploughed and cleared to be utilized for small-hold organic farming.

This research generally aimed to characterize the attributes of smallholder organic vegetable farmers, their production practices and problems and document best practices as bases for policy directions to ensure the sustainability of small-holder organic farming in the country.

Materials and methods

Project Sites and Respondents

The study was conducted in the CAR, specifically in the province of Benguet. The Region consists of the provinces of Abra, Apayao, Benguet, Ifugao, Kalinga and Mountain Province and the highly urbanized city of Baguio. With an elevation of 2,928 meters above sea level, the CAR is the only land-locked region in the Philippines. It produces 65% to 80% of the Philippines' supply of temperate-climate vegetables mainly potato, cabbage, beans and carrots (Gimenez & Bagyan, 2004).

The study's respondents consisted of 31 certified organic vegetable producers who were all members of the La Trinidad Organic Practitioners (La Top) Multi-Purpose Cooperative. La Top (henceforth referred to as the Cooperative) is a certified organic vegetable producer certified by the Organic Certification Center of the Philippines. La Top is one of numerous multi-purpose cooperatives and peoples organizations in the CAR organized mainly for the marketing of products like Arabica coffee, heirloom rice and vegetables. The 31 respondents consisted of the 20 originally certified members and 11 members who were in the process certification. At the time of the study, the Cooperative has 55 members, 20 were certified and 35 in the process of certification. The study was delimited to this number. The study intended to involve all the 55 members but due to time limitation as well as the accessibility of the organic farms, only 31 farmers were included.

Data Collection and Analysis

Survey method through the use of a researcher-made questionnaire was the primary data gathering technique. The survey was done by personal interviews and ocular inspection of the organic farms

for a first hand observation of the farm practices. Telephone inquiries or short messaging system (SMS) were also utilized when some information were missed out during the interview and to verify vague and incomplete information.

To supplement data gathered, archival research and benchmarking were done. Existing literature available on line were accessed. Other unpublished materials like flyers, pamphlets and other IEC materials deemed related to the present study were also considered as sources of benchmark data. The PCARRD Information Bulletin Series for Vegetable Production found online was also used as reference.

Descriptive statistics was used to qualify and summarize descriptive data. The descriptive part defined and assessed the organic vegetable production and systems. Tools used in descriptive analysis included frequency counts, percentages and means/averages. Findings are presented using tables, graphs and figs.

Results and discussion

Basic Attributes of Organic Vegetable Farmers

The succeeding tables present and describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the vegetable producers and the trainings they have attended.

Thirty one (31) organic producers were interviewed in the CAR who was all members of the La Trinidad Organic Practitioners (La Top) Multi-Purpose Cooperative, Inc. Of this number, 20 were the first farmers originally certified by the OCCP. Under the star rank classification of the Internal Control System of the Cooperative, 19 percent are 1-3 star and 81 percent are 4-6 star farm-owners. Ranks are indicative of how long and how intense one had been practicing organic farming. Farming is still typically a man's work as almost 65 percent of the respondents are males. Noteworthy, however, is the increasing proportion of women who are now engaged in farming in general, and in organic production, in particular. The mean age of organic farmers in the CAR is 46 but about 39 percent are already over 55 years old.

Eighty (80) percent are married, with three (3) children, on the average. In terms of educational attainment, more and more professionals are engaged in organic farming as seen by the number of respondents who are college graduates or higher which is more than 32 percent. Almost all have undergone basic trainings on organic farming and have continued to undergo more advanced trainings in this area.

Table 1a. Demographic attributes of organic farmers.

Attribute	Farm Rank		Total	
	1-3 Star	4-6 Star	N	%
Age				
35 and below	2	3	5	16.13
36-40	3	3	6	19.35
41-45		2	2	6.45
46-50		6	6	19.35
51-55	1	6	7	22.58
56 and above		5	5	16.13
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Mean Age: 46.06≈46				
Gender				
Male	2	18	20	64.52
Female	4	7	11	35.48
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Civil Status				
Single	1	3	4	12.90
Married	5	20	25	80.65
Widow/er		2	2	6.45
Total	6	25	31	100.00
No. of Children				
None		3	3	11.11
1 – 3	4	8	12	44.44
4 – 6	1	7	8	29.63
7 and more		4	4	14.81
Total	5	22	27	100.00
Ave.# of Children: 3				
Highest Educational Attainment				
Elementary Graduate	1		1	3.23
High School Undergrad		1	1	3.23
High School Graduate	2	5	7	22.58
College Undergraduate	1	6	7	22.58
College Graduate		9	9	29.03
Vocational/Technical	2	3	5	16.13
Doctorate		1	1	3.23
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Attended Organic Farming Trainings?				
Yes	6	24	30	96.77
No		1	1	3.23
Total	6	25	31	100.00

The socio-economic characteristics of the organic producers are presented in Table 1b. With an average farm area of only more than 600 square meters, organic farming in the CAR is characterized as small-hold with farmers cultivating only a small parcel of land.

Table 1b. Socio-economic attributes of organic producers.

Attribute	Farm Rank		Total	
	1-3 Stars	4-6 Stars	N	%
Farm Area (m2)				
250 and below		2	2	6.45
251-500	3	11	14	45.16
501-750		1	1	3.23
751-1000	1		1	3.23
1001 and above	2	11	13	41.94
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Ave. Farm Area: 654m ²				
Tenure				
Owner	5	21	26	83.87
Owner+Caretaker		1	1	3.23
Owner+ Tenant		1	1	3.23
Owner+Leasee		1	1	3.23
Caretaker		1	1	3.23
Leasee	1		1	3.23
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Years Engaged in Organic Farming				
5 years & below	5	5	10	32.26
6 – 10	1	17	18	58.06
11- 15		1	1	3.23
16 – 20		1	1	3.23
21 & above		1	1	3.23
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Ave. No. of Years in OA: 8 years				
Farming as Only Source of Income				
Yes	1	11	12	38.71
No	5	14	19	61.29
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Other Sources of Income				
Employment		2	2	10.53
Pension		2	2	10.53
Barangay Kagawad/Tanod		2	2	10.53
Marketing		1	1	5.26
Manufacturing		1	1	5.26
Agribusiness/Food Processing/Beekeeping		5	6	31.58
Laborer	1		3	15.79
Forest Ranger	3	1	1	5.26
Freelance Insurance Agent	1		1	5.26
Total	5	14	19	100.00
Annual Net Income from Farming				
50,000 and below			15	48.39
50,001 – 100,000	4	11	8	25.81
100,001 – 150,000	2	6	2	6.45
150,001 – 200,000		2	2	6.45
200,001 – 250,000		1	1	3.23
250,001 – 300,000		1	1	3.23
300,001 and above		2	2	6.45
Total	6	25	31	100.00
Average Annual Net Income from Farming: Php 98,387.39				
Annual Income from Other Sources				
50,000 and below			10	52.63
50,001 – 100,000	4	6	2	10.53
100,001 – 150,000	1	1	1	5.26
150,001 – 200,000		1	1	5.26
200,001 – 250,000		4	4	21.05
250,001 – 300,000				
300,001 and above			2	10.53
Total		2	19	100.00
Average Annual Income from other Sources: Php: 109,210.82	5	14		

About 42 percent of the producers, however, own more than 1,000 square meters of farm. More than 83

percent own the land they till while the rest are caretakers, tenants or leasers in combination with being owners. More than half of the organic farmers have been engaged in the trade for 6-10 years. On the average, they have been practicing organic farming for eight (8) years, long before the enactment of the Organic Agriculture Act of 2010. Only about 39 percent depend solely on farming as a source of income. Of those who have other sources of livelihood outside farming, majority derive income from farming-related activities like agribusiness, food processing or

beekeeping. Others are regular office employees while some have their own businesses. The average annual net income derived from organic farming is almost one hundred thousand pesos (P98,387.39). However, almost half of the organic farmers learn much lesser than fifty thousand pesos. Of those who do not depend solely on farming as livelihood, the average annual income they earn is quite higher than what they earn from farming (Php109,210.82). Table 1c presents the organic and non-organic farming-related trainings, seminars or workshops attended by the farmers.

Table 1c. Trainings, Seminars, or Workshops Attended.

Name of Training, Seminar or Workshop	Frequency	Percent
Basic Organic Agriculture		
- Practical organic agriculture		
- Organic farming techniques		
- Compost preparation, vermiculture and vermicomposting		
- Mulching		
- Bio-organic pesticide	33	47.83
- Preparation/fermentation of biological pesticides		
- Certificate course for practitioners of organic agriculture		
- Organic agriculture appreciation		
- Organic materials for pesticides and fertilizers		
- Basic organic farming/gardening		
Advanced organic agriculture		
- Awareness on judicious use of pesticides	5	7.25
- Bio-dynamic organic farming		
- Sustainable agriculture		
Other organic agriculture related seminar		
- Internal control system and orientation on organic farming/ Internal control system for organic group certification		
- International certification		
- Farm inspector training		
- Pest clinic	13	18.84
- Training on enhancement of organic inspection and certification/national and local organic certification accreditation		
- Organic-based vegetable production course		
- Agri-tourism organic farmers training		
- Philippine National Standards for organic agriculture		
Other non-organic agriculture-related seminars/trainings		
- Beekeeping		
- Farm business planning training		
- Farmer's field school		
- Komamoto (Japanese Piggery Technology)	18	26.09
- Packaging and labelling		
- Cooperative pre-membership seminar		
- Good agriculture practices (GMP)		
Total	69	100.00
Sponsoring Agency		
Cooperative		
Government organizations		
- Academe (Benguet State University)		
- Department of Agriculture-CAR		
- Agricultural Training Institute		
- Department of Science and Technology		
- Food and Agriculture Organization-United Nations		
Non-Government Organization (Jaime Ongpin Foundation)		
Others (Private individuals)		

The farmer-respondents have attended basic as well as advanced training, seminars, short courses and workshops on OA and other related or non-related fields. Almost one-half have trainings on the basic principles of OA under topics like Practical Organic Agriculture, Basic Organic Farming/Gardening, Organic Agriculture Appreciation, Organic Farming Techniques and Certificate Course for Practitioners of Organic Agriculture. More than seven (7) percent have advanced training on OA which included Awareness on Judicious Use of Pesticides, Bio-Dynamic Organic Farming and Sustainable Agriculture.

With the development of new technologies on organic farming, it is important for farmers to enhance their knowledge and improve their practices. Almost 19 percent have undergone orientation and enhancement training on Internal Control System and Certification as well as on farm inspection. They have also training or orientations on National and International Standards for certification. Other training related to OA which they have attended included Pest Clinic, Organic-based Vegetable Production Course and Agri-Tourism Organic Farmers Training. More than 26 percent have acquired knowledge and skills on areas outside OA which prepared them to become agri-entrepreneurs. These are in the areas of beekeeping, farm business planning, Komamoto (Japanese Piggery Technology), packaging and labelling and good manufacturing practices (GMP).

Various government and non-government agencies have been tasked to provide avenues for the continuous acquisition of knowledge and skills by this sector of society. Aside from the Cooperative, the Benguet State University, which pioneered organic agriculture in the CAR, in collaboration with the Regional Offices of the Department of Agriculture (DA), Department of Science and Technology (DOST) and the Agricultural Training Institute (ATI), provide farmers with trainings to enhance their know-how. The Jaime V. Ongpin Foundation, a non-government organization, takes an active part in the promotion of OA in the country by providing technical and

financial assistance to farmers. Private individuals also share their knowledge and expertise on the basics of organic farming by mentoring fellow farmers.

Production Practices and Systems

Crops Raised

The organic production of vegetables is generally described as a system where different kinds and/or varieties of vegetables are found and raised in complement with or intercropped with the other to maximize the production area. Aside from vegetables, there are also herbs, spices, rootcrops, fruit trees and ornamentals. This research focused on the analysis of 11 different kinds and/or varieties of beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*, snap bean and French bean varieties), broccoli (*Brassica oleracea var. italica*), cabbage (*Brassica oleracea var. capitata*), carrots (*Daucus carota subsp. Sativus*), cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea var. botrytis*), cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*, native and Japanese cucumber varieties), lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*, fancy varieties), pechay (*Brassica rapa subsp. oleifera* and *Brassica rapa subsp. chinensis*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*), spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* New Zealand and Japanese spinach varieties) and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* big and cherry tomato varieties).

At one given time, depending on the area available, the farmers plant at most 18 and at least three (3) different crops. Lettuce, broccoli, snap beans and New Zealand spinach, carrots and small (cherry) tomato, Japanese spinach, French beans, flowering pechay, cabbage, other cucumber variety, potato, cauliflower, Japanese cucumber and large tomato are most frequently planted. Lettuce is always the main crop of organic farmers in the CAR due to its high demand in the market. In addition to this, lettuce has a short production period ranging from a month to one and a half months.

Land area planted

Since organic farmers are required to practice production techniques like crop rotation, intercropping, relay cropping and multi-story cropping, the actual area planted to a particular crop can only be estimated.

These techniques are useful to avoid mono-culture system, to improve farm productivity, and to ensure high quality produce.

It is estimated that at any given production period, the farmer plants, on the average, less than one-fifth (about 256 square meters) of his land area with vegetables. About 185 square meters is planted with other organic crops. The rest of the area is left unproductive as a source of compost materials. The estimated aggregate production area is apportioned with the selected vegetables as follows (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Percentage of production area planted with selected vegetables.

Of the estimated aggregate area that the farmer plants with the selected vegetables, only three products account for at least 10 percent of the total. These are lettuce (13%), snap beans (12%) and broccoli (11%). All the rest account for only less than 10 percent of the area with cauliflower and large tomato having the least areas at one (1) percent each.

Production Schedule

A little more than 87 percent of the farmers plan their production schedule. The rest who do not plan say they just practice bio-intensive farming which means maximizing the production capacity of the land while at the same time practicing crop rotation or parallel cropping but also taking market needs as consideration. Of those who plan their production schedule, planning is based on the considerations presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Basis for crop production schedule.

Production season is still the primary basis for scheduling when a crop is planted by almost half (48%) of the farmers. This is followed by market forecast or demand (24%). This indicates that a significant number of producers are driven by market demand in the production of a particular crop. Crop rotation is also a consideration in planning production. The farmers avoid monoculture in order to produce better quality harvest. Other bases in planning production schedule are season/weather (5%) and La Top programming (5%). Some farmers time their production schedule to avoid excessive rainfall or changes in climatic conditions while there are also those who just follow a programming schedule given them by the Cooperative. Multiple cropping is also a basis in planning production. This is indicated by almost three (3%) of the producers.

Table 2. Average area devoted for organic vegetable production.

Indicators	Average	Percent
Average area planted with selected organic vegetables (m2)	256	18.00
Average area planted with other organic crops (m2)	185	13.00
Average area intended for other purposes	984	69.00

Crop Programming

In crop programming, the farmers are often guided by the concept of “heavy-giver, heavy-eater”. As long as this practice is followed, there is no need for them to follow a rigid schedule of what crop to produce and when to produce a sequence of the crops to rise. Table 3 enumerates the different crop programming practices of the farmers in the CAR.

Table 3. Crop programming practices.

Crop Programming
brassicas-legumes-leafy
leafy-leafy-fruited
leafy-legumes-root crops
root crops-leafy-leafy-legumes
leafy-brassicas-root crops
brassicas-leafy
legumes-leafy
legumes-leafy-root crops-fruited
root crops-leafy-legumes
leafy-legume
leafy-legumes-legumes-root crops
brassicas-leafy-legumes
legumes-leafy-fruited
leafy-legumes-fruited
leafy-legumes-leafy
leafy-leafy-legumes
root crops-leafy-brassicas

The farmer-members of the Cooperative practice at most 17 types of crop programming schedules involving two (2) to four (4) crops or five (5) different families that include leafy vegetables, legumes, root crops, brassicas and fruited vegetables. These are done to maintain soil quality and to prevent the occurrence of pests and diseases.

Table 4. Production season for selected vegetables.

Season of cultivation	Vegetable type
Year-round	Lettuce (romaine variety), tomato (cherry), flowering pechay, French beans, New Zealand spinach
Cooler months	Lettuce (iceberg & looseleaf varieties), carrots, broccoli, cabbage, potato, pechay (pakchoi & chingkang varieties), snap beans, Japanese spinach, cauliflower, cucumber

In terms of cultivation time of the selected vegetables, some are cultivated year-round while others thrive only during cooler months of the year. Though looseleaf and iceberg lettuce varieties are cultivated only during cooler months, the romaine variety could be cultivated year round in the presence of a greenhouse. Cherry tomato is raised throughout the year but other tomato varieties are planted during summer to avoid excessive rain, when there is no greenhouse. The cultivation of carrots and broccoli is also timed during cooler months if there are no greenhouses. The production season of the other vegetables, seen in Table 4.

Production Inputs and Sources

Organic vegetables production is characterized by limited supply of inputs particularly direct materials used for production such as seeds, fertilizers and pesticides. Seeds are either produced in the farm or bought. Seeds produced in the farm are pechay, cherry tomato, snap beans, French beans, New Zealand spinach and Japanese spinach. The farmers also practice barter of seeds if their produce is more than enough for their use. Seeds are bought either from farm supply stores, local seed companies or seed dealers. Seeds purchased are broccoli, cucumber, carrots, cabbage, lettuce and cauliflower. The unavailability of organically produced or certified seeds is a seeming constraint of the industry in the CAR. Farmers cannot claim to be 100 percent organic producers because the seeds they use were not raised organically.

Compost fertilizers and botanical pesticides are available from farm supply stores but are expensive and limited in quantity. Thus, the farmers produce their own fertilizers using farm by-products. With the introduction of technologies learned from their attendance to trainings and seminars, they produce inputs using microbial preparations and earthworms. The farmers do not only produce traditional compost but also vermicompost/vermicast and products using “Mokusako” or wood vinegar technology.

As shown in Fig. 3, almost three-fourths of the farmers still practice traditional composting technology to produce fertilizers. About 40 percent have infused Mokusako technology in their traditional composting technique while 16 percent produce vermicompost or vermicast using earthworms given them free by the DA. Since the farmers are encouraged to prepare their own inputs using waste by-products in the farm, they allocate a portion of their farm for sources of raw materials used for composting. Aside from grasses, weeds and leaves found in the farm or garden, the most commonly utilized plants found in abundance in the farm are sunflower (*Helianthus*), commonly referred to as “marapait” napier grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*), sugar cane (*Saccharum officinarum*),

banana (*Musa balbisiana Colla cv.*) stalk and locally referred to plants like “alnus”, “caliandra”, and “alunit”. Sometimes, fresh or carbonized rice hull are also used. To hasten the decomposition of these plants or improve their nutrient contents, molasses, effective microorganism (EMO), fish amino acid (fish emulsion), fermented plant juice (FPJ) or manure from their free-range chickens or carabao are added.

Fig. 3. Kinds of fertilizer used.

The farmers also use bio-organic fertilizers to enhance production. With the addition of activators and enhancers like EMO and FPJ to compost and vermicompost, compost tea and vermitea are produced. These are applied to crops as basal or foliar fertilizer. By-products from the use of “Mokusako” technology are used as bio-fertilizer. The farmers had also experimented on and found effective uses for natural and kitchen waste materials as sources of nutrients. This includes rice washing, rice wine, fish emulsion, yeast and lime. The extensive use of molasses from sugar cane, fruits and vegetables, is noted.

Raw materials are bought (79%), obtained free (16%) or produced in the farm (5%). The Cooperative also sells molasses, EMOs and FPJs to farmers. The need for raw materials has produced a few enterprising farmers who procure fresh rice hull, molasses and cow manure from established sources outside the Region and sell them to their fellow farmers. The DA provides free materials to farmers like vermicast, earthworms (African night crawlers), molasses or FPJs and EMOs when farmers attend agency-sponsored trainings or seminars. Farmers who have large areas to cultivate plant sugar cane as source for molasses. Their excess is given to fellow farmers for free (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Sources of raw materials for fertilizer.

The control of pests and insects is primarily done by intercropping attractant or repellent crops. Some farmers literally get rid of pests and insects by killing them manually by hand or feet. Others spray their own concoction which is a combination of fermented chili, ginger, garlic and gin which have been proven effective in eliminating pests and insects. The farmers continue to experiment on natural materials found within the garden as pesticides and insecticides.

Other supplies used indirectly in production include farm machineries and those used in the construction of greenhouses. Shredders, chopping machines and grass cutters are used in the preparation of compost. More than half (58%) of the farmers have their own shredder. Almost one fourth own a chopping machine while 12 percent have a grass cutter. Nine (9) percent of the farmers have neither of these machineries so shredding is done manually. The Cooperative offers farmers these machineries on instalment basis or rent-to-own scheme. One enterprising farmer fabricates shredders for commercial purposes.

Most common farm structures are greenhouses and nurseries but most greenhouses also serve as nurseries. Greenhouses are made of steel or bamboo posts with UV-treated plastic as covering. Bamboo poles are also used as trellises or anchors for climbing beans and cucumbers.

Labor

Organic farming in the CAR is basically a family enterprise involving 1-3 family members performing the whole cycle of farm work up to the disposal of the produce. This is presented in Fig. 5.

Three-fourths of the organic farms depend on family labor while more than one-fourth depend on full time laborers to do the work in the farm. There are farms which combine both family labor and parttime labor. But there are also farms which depend just on family members to do the work. The farms which employ fulltime labors also employ part time labors. Both types of labors are paid either on a daily or monthly basis; parttime labors are paid on a daily basis while fulltime labors are paid on a monthly basis but there are instances where parttime labors get their remunerations at the end of each week. Average daily rate of labor is 250.00 pesos inclusive of meals and snacks. Average monthly labor rate is about 4500.00 which may include lodging and meals.

Fig. 5. Distribution of Farm Labor.

The farmers normally hire part time labourers to gather materials for compost making and to prepare the farm prior to production. For compost preparation, the farmers hire at least two (2) labourers for two days on the average. They make compost at least once a month. On land preparation, at least one labourer is hired to work three (3) days on the average every one and a half months. If the labourer is hired to do both of the activity, at least two are needed, working 12 days on the average as frequent as every one and a half months. For the rest of the production cycle, family labor is utilized.

Production Volume

Annual production volume estimates for each crop can be seen in the Fig. 6. Estimates were used since the actual production area for crops at any given period is not fixed because of the practice of multiple cropping and intercropping. Aside from this, some crops,

particularly lettuce and pechay are seeded by some farmers every one or two weeks ensuring a continuous harvest for these crops year-round. Production also depends on the presence of a greenhouse.

Fig. 6. Estimated annual production volume.

Table 5. Average yield per square meter per cycle.

Crop	Yield (kg/m2)
Snap beans	1.4
French beans	1.2
Broccoli	1.6
Cabbage	2.0
Carrots	1.5
Cauliflower	3.1
Japanese cucumber	1.3
Other cucumber varieties	1.7
Lettuce	0.9
Flowering pechay	1.1
Pakchoi/chingkan pechay	1.0
Potato	1.7
New Zealand spinach	1.4
Japanese spinach	1.1
Cherry tomato	2.7
Large tomato	2.9

Based on the estimated average aggregate area planted with the selected organic vegetables, production volume is highest for lettuce which is about 7000 kilograms annually, followed by flowering pechay (3630kg.), chingkan and pakchoi pechay varieties (3178kg.), New Zealand spinach (2466kg.) and broccoli (2424kg.). Cherry tomato, snap beans, carrots and Japanese spinach production is from 1000 to almost 1900 kilograms annually. Crops with annual production volume between 500 kilograms and 1000 kilograms are French beans (953kg.), Japanese cucumber (750kg.), and cabbage (645kg.). Production is less than 500 kilograms annually for cauliflower (470kg.), potato (452kg.), native/other cucumber varieties (436kg.) and large tomato (118kg.). The average yield per square meter is presented in Table 5.

Yield for leafy vegetables ranges from less than 1 kilogram to almost 1.5 kilograms per square meter. New Zealand spinach yields the highest with 1.4 kilograms. This spinach variety requires very little cultural management yet produces very high yields. Though yield for lettuce is less than 1 kilogram per square meter, production is still intensive. Very high yields are produced for tomato which is less than 3 kilograms per square meter with yield for large tomato (2.9kg.) slightly higher than cherry tomato (2.7kg). Cucumber, another fruiting vegetable yields 1.5 kilograms on the average with native cucumber variety producing higher than the Japanese variety. Yield for rootcrops (carrots and potato) is more than 1.5 kilograms per square meter, on the average. Among the vegetables under study, cauliflower produces the highest yield per square meter at 3.1 kilograms while broccoli which belongs to the same family yields only 1.6 kilograms for the same area.

Source of capital

Majority of the farmers (81.82%) use their own savings as capital for production. Others (15.15%) borrow capital from the Cooperative to finance their production. This is in the form of production loan which is one of the products offered by the Cooperative. Only small portions (3.03%) of the farmers depend on their relatives when in need of capital for their production.

Recording system

About three-fourths of the organic producers keep farm records, in their own way. The others keep records sometimes or keep no records at all. Those who do not keep records say they don't have any knowledge about record-keeping while one doesn't really know how to read nor write.

Those who have records keep production or marketing-related records. The most frequent record kept is that of "sales/marketing" followed by "record of expenses" and "farm activities". Others keep farm diaries and production plan schedules. Nursery activities, harvest and seedling production are sometimes also recorded.

How frequent do they record? About one half of the farmers do their recording every day. Others record only when they have made a "sales" or "expense" transaction. Some make records only every production period while others record every time they do farm activities.

Production and farm facilities

In a typical organic farm, three (3) basic structures can be found, a nursery, a greenhouse and a composting facility. In the CAR, it is common that the greenhouse also serves as nursery. Only few farms have separate structures for greenhouse and nursery. There are about 2-3 small greenhouses in a farm but generally only one big greenhouse can be seen. Within each greenhouse are plots sometimes enclosed in concrete hollow blocks but oftentimes are not. Standard plot sizes range from 10m² to 15m². Most of the greenhouses are made of bamboo posts and covered with UV-treated plastic or mesh net. Only a few of the greenhouses are made of sturdy materials like steel posts.

Composting facilities are shed-type with paved or unpaved floorings. The farmers do their shredding in these sheds. Shredded materials are placed in concrete enclosures to decompose further with the addition of microorganisms or vermin.

Aside from the above structures, other facilities found in some of the farms are multi-purpose structures serving as stock rooms or packing houses. It is more common that packing is done in the farmer's own house. For irrigation, spring is the most common source of water. Hoses are used to connect the farm to the source. Others have built water reservoirs as source of water for irrigation.

There are eight (8) Cooperative members who were contracted by the ATI-CAR to serve as training centers for Organic Farming. In which case, additional structure is found in the farm, that is, a training room.

Marketing functions performed by producers.

Immediately before bringing their produce to the market, the farmers perform simple and basic postharvest or pre-marketing functions. However, these do not add value to the products.

Fig. 7 shows the activities done by the farmer before the products are brought to the market. Most activities are done as quality control measures. These are done in the farm itself or in a temporary holding area which maybe in the farmer’s house. Other farmers have their own packing house where pre-marketing activities are done.

Fig. 7. Marketing functions performed by producers.

Trimming or cutting is made on broccoli, cabbage, carrots and cauliflower. For broccoli, the leaves are removed and cut accordingly into a mushroom cut (the head and at least 8” of the stem is retained). This is also done for cauliflower and sometimes prepared into a “cook-all” form. For cabbage, the outer or mature part of the head is usually removed. Carrots are trimmed of leaves from the shoulder portion. It is also washed and air dried.

Cucumber, tomato, carrots and potato are also often sorted or segregated according to size. Leafy vegetables like lettuce and pechay are washed off dirt, if needed. All vegetables are weighed and packed in plastic and labeled with the Cooperative label bearing

the farm name and the farm star rank. Excluding cabbage, cauliflower and broccoli, which are packed on a per piece basis, all the vegetables are packed into 250 gram packs for affordability. There is a temporary storage for vegetables which are harvested in the afternoon and marketed on the next day. Otherwise, all vegetables are gathered very early in the morning to be brought to market as fresh as possible.

Marketing arrangement

This refers to how the produce is brought to the market. Less than 90 percent of the farmers deliver their produce to the Cooperative office or to the nearest Cooperative outlet in their area. For those who sell to their neighbors, their neighbors personally go to their houses or farms to buy. As to other traders or buyers, arrangement is also “for delivery”. Farmers with buyers in Manila send orders through the Victory Liner (a bus company) cargo box which leaves Baguio City every day at 9:00 P.M. Porter fee and waybill are charged to the consignee and included in their statement of accounts.

Frequency of sales

Frequency of sales depends on harvestability of the crop and on orders made. While 14 percent are able to sell different crops on a daily basis, more than 66 percent are able to deliver to their outlets two to three times a week on the average. About 20 percent sell only once a week. Normally for Manila outlets, delivery is twice a week usually either Tuesdays or Wednesdays and Fridays and Saturdays.

Marketing costs incurred

Marketing expenses incurred by the farmer are in the form of the packaging material, label and transport cost. Labels are bought from the Cooperative while polybags are brought from the market. Transport cost is the farmer’s fare while bringing his/her product to the nearest outlet in his/her area or gasoline for his/her vehicle.

Production Constraints

The critical issues affecting the production of organic temperate vegetables fall into five major categories.

Natural calamities

The production of temperate vegetables is most affected by the forces of nature particularly typhoons. Production is halted during strong typhoons that bring heavy rains and strong winds. This results to damages of greenhouses, incurrance of losses, and halt in production resulting to lower production and lower income. The general phenomenon of climate change where excessive rainfall is experienced as well as extreme conditions of hot and cold temperatures often results in damage to crops due to wilting, rotting and decay.

Pest management

The occurrence of pests, insects and diseases and their control is expectedly a major concern in organic farming. This generally results in unattractive plants which are unappealing to consumers in the market. Insect infestation often results in poor or low quality produce or crop failure. Though there are available botanical pesticides in stores, most farmers cannot afford to buy them so they make their own concoctions to remedy the problem. Others resort to manually getting rid of pests and insects. In cases where infestation is massive, farmers hire additional labor just to do the job. This results in higher production cost for the farmer.

Production inputs

Farmers are encouraged to produce their own production inputs due to the limited supply in the market. The limited supply compounded by the high cost of inputs result in a high cost of production for the farmer. The quality of inputs, particularly seeds determines the quality of produce. Low quality inputs results in low quality outputs which subsequently affect production and income. The vegetable industry had been the beneficiary of the DA program on the promotion of hybrid varieties for vegetable production. It was noted by Aguiba (2005) as cited by Johnson *et al.* (2008) that budget constraints in DA mean that in some cases, ordinary vegetable seed rather than

hybrids are being recommended. Greater uptake of hybrids and the consequent increased yields could significantly enhance yields and profitability, and increase competitiveness of the industry against imports.

Lack of capital

Since most of the organic vegetable growers in the CAR are subsistence farmers, they lack capital for farming. If some turn to friends and relatives when in need of capital for the next production cycle, others avail of the loan facilities of the Cooperative for their production needs. This is often in the form of a production loan. Production loan is offered at the rate of 1.5 percent-2.0 percent monthly that is payable within a period agreed upon by the member but not to exceed one (1) year.

Other problems

Other production concerns which generally result in low production and low income include, plant management, lack of manpower, irrigation and lack of capital. Some farmers in the CAR are concerned about scientific crop production including plant management, like timing NPK to the different stages of crop growth. If organic vegetable production could be done scientifically, nutrient deficiency of the soil could also be addressed. Manpower is also a problem for farmers in the CAR in the case of those who have gainful employment and could not devote 100 percent of their time to do farm activities. In this regard they have to hire fulltime or parttime laborers to do farm works. Irrigation problem affects almost all the organic farms in the study. Because of elevation, farms in the CAR experience shortage of water needed to irrigate the crops. Although some farms source water from springs, these dry up during summer. Aside from this, the source may be too far from the farm.

Best Practices Documented

The research documented the best practices of farmers in the production of organic vegetables as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Best Practices Documented.

Best Practice	Pioneering Farm/ Contact Person	Coverage of Operation	Innovation/Creativity Made
Adoption of Mokusako technology to produce compost fertilizer	Lily of the Valley Farm/ Jefferson Laruan	In-house production of Mokusako using materials which are farm-sourced	Products and by-products of the technology are used in vegetable production
Follow a planting schedule based on the requirements of contract buyers		Technology product and by-products are used as foliar and basal fertilizer for brassicas	Yield is 6kg per square meter for broccoli and cauliflower and 4.5kg per square meter for cabbage
		Follow a production schedule for a six-month period given by contract buyers	Demand-driven production schedule insures market for produce and eliminates losses
		Production is concentrated on 6 specified vegetables required	

Conclusion

Though farming is considered a man’s work, women’s role in farming is increasing. Smallholder organic farmers are middle-aged probably because they used to engage in conventional farming or have previous careers. More and more professionals are engaging in organic farming as seen by the number of respondents who are at least college graduates. The average annual income of about one hundred thousand pesos that farmers get from tilling an average farm area of 600 square meters is not sufficient enough for their needs so they also engage in other livelihood activities such as agribusiness, food processing and beekeeping. The farmers continue to improve their knowledge and skills on OA through the help of government and non-government organizations. The production of organic vegetables is a system where various kinds and/or varieties of vegetables are found and raised in the production area intercropped with and complemented by herbs, spices, root crops, fruit trees and ornamentals in order to maximize the area. Production season, market demand and crop rotation are main considerations in planning their production schedule. Due to limited supply and high cost of production inputs, farmers produce their own fertilizers and pesticides using technologies acquired from trainings attended and those they have personally produced by experimentation. Smallholder organic vegetable farming in the CAR is a family enterprise involving 1-3 family members performing the whole cycle of farm

work up to the disposal of farm produce. Some farmers have already perfected organic production technologies and cultural management practices for some crops resulting to higher yields compared with those produced the conventional way. The farmers use their own savings for production although the Cooperative, some government agencies and non-government organizations offer soft loan to farmers who need capitalization. The farmers keep simple records of production, farm activities, sales and expenses as regularly as they can. Three basic structures can be found in the farm- a nursery, a greenhouse and a composting facility. Spring water is the most common source of irrigation. The farmers perform simple and basic pre-marketing functions as quality control measures but do not add to the value of the products.

Production is most affected by natural calamities, infestation, limited and high cost of production inputs, lack of capital, lack of manpower and irrigation which result to low production and low income. The production of compost fertilizer utilizing Mokusako technology and applied on the production of brassicas produced much higher yields per square than the average recorded. Following a production schedule based on the requirement of contract buyers within a specified period and for specified vegetables assures ready market for the products and eliminates losses. These are the best practices documented in the study.

Technologies for the production of sustainable, certified inputs need to be developed, improved and standardized and make farmer's access to these technologies and resources greater in order to reduce cost, increase production and improve income. The adoption of climate change mitigating measures and improving crop resiliency could only be done by intensifying capability building mechanisms of small-hold organic farmers. The government and the private sector must pool their resources together to address these constraints and sustain small-hold organic vegetable production in the CAR.

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